

Climate Change: Re-Architecting A Legacy Meteorological Gateway For A Rapidly Evolving Computing Environment

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Abstract—This case study highlights the initial work and challenges faced when converting the organically grown gateway underlying the Midwest Regional Climate Center to a modern, extensible framework and composable platform. Issues confronted range from untangling undocumented scripts, multiple databases & user accounts, hundreds of scheduled processes, and decades of accumulated data dispersed across multiple machines.

Keywords—gateway, meteorology, climatology, case study

I. INTRODUCTION

The Midwestern Regional Climate Center (MRCC) is a cooperative program between the National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI) and Purdue University in West Lafayette, Indiana. It is a partner in a national climate service program that includes NCEI, five other Regional Climate Centers, and State Climate Offices [1]. The MRCC serves the nine-state Midwest region (Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Kentucky, Michigan, Minnesota, Missouri, Ohio, and Wisconsin). Its services and research help to better explain climate and its impacts on the Midwest, provide practical solutions to specific climate problems, and allows them to develop information for the Midwest on climate-sensitive issues such as agriculture, climate change, energy, the environment, human health, risk management, transportation, and water resources. Offering online meteorological tools and data, a gateway developed over the course of the several years of its operation.

In 2021, the center transitioned from the University of Illinois to Purdue University. Upon transfer and returning the gateway to service, the complexity and difficulty of alterations to the code quickly became apparent and spurred an initiative to modernize it. Purdue University's Research Computing department was recruited to deconstruct and re-architect the MRCC gateway to allow for easier code maintenance, extensibility, sustainability, and a more structured approach to data management.

II. CHALLENGES

The numerous sub-applications, scripts, and overall architecture had developed organically—no overarching framework, specification, or structure—over the course of a

couple decades. Consequently, changes and additions to the gateway weren't always made with anticipation of potential future needs and how those may integrate with or affect the existing system and its maintenance. Troubling points and challenges included:

- Little to no documentation on the purpose or functionality of scripts.
- Scripts were recognizably authored by numerous people with little sense of a cohesive whole or conformance to any standard.
- Lack of code versioning and management tools, such as GIT or Subversion. Numerous versions of files with slight variance in names (e.g., file, file_old, etc), sometimes with no indication as to the one currently being used.
- Despite using the robust server-side language JSP for many of the gateway's pages, there was little use of its advantages such as variables for oft-repeated values, templating, and state management.
- Gigabytes of generated images, data, and files, many of which were no longer relevant or used.

Issues were further compounded by scripts, data, and untold numbers of CRON tasks spread across multiple machines with little clear division of responsibility coupled with undocumented manual workflows.

III. RE-ARCHITECTURE

Re-architecting a system that grew over the course of decades would be no small task and started by addressing some of the more vocalized complaints.

A. Composable Environment

To address scalability and potentially ease the alteration of existing or introduction of new data workflows, Geddes was utilized. Geddes is an “on-premise Kubernetes-based private cloud at Purdue University and was designed to meet the increased demand for the deployment of flexible, persistent, edge and supporting services for scientific data analysis” [4].

The gateway is composed of a few simple services such as a database server (MariaDB), web server (Nginx + PHP-FPM),

and shared storage mounted across them. Along with this, the composable infrastructure allows for building scalable data ingestion and processing pipelines utilizing Docker containers.

B. Content Management System

Composed of largely hard-coded individual JSP pages, the MRCC gateway required manual alteration of code to perform simple tasks such as updating the text of a page or posting a news item. Representatives of the MRCC expressed the desire for a system that would allow them to, among other things:

- Easily update existing content, preferably without modifying scripts.
- Gate access to specific pages or entire applications.
- Track visitations/usage (required for some reporting).
- Add new tools and content with relative ease.
- Site must be ADA compliant.
- API or other mechanism to quickly extract data for new uses/tools.

The Purdue team decided to use Halcyon [2], a content management system (CMS) developed in-house as it brought many of the desired features out of the box. Although initially intended for managing HPC center operations, the structure and flexibility of the platform easily lended itself to the task. Halcyon is built upon the popular web application framework Laravel [3], which provides a number of utilities that would be employed in the porting of MRCC applications, such as a robust command-line tool, templating system, mail & notification handling, task scheduling, and easy integrations with services such as LDAP and message queue systems.

C. Applications

Aside from more traditional, static informational pages the MRCC gateway consists of multiple sub-sites or applications. These tended to fall into three categories:

- A grouping of primarily static informational pages.
- Browsable/filterable data pulled from various databases.
- Interactive, single-page applications typically presented as a map with filters.

Where possible, the first two were ported as modules, extensions to the CMS that consist of logical groupings based on the data being handled, tasks, and interfaces. Modules may implement their own functionality, APIs, databases, and even themes while still having access to the central CMS and its users.

A particular challenge of the application porting was the existence of multiple login systems and user accounts. That is, there was no shared, central user identity. Instead, each sub-application of the gateway maintained its own database, and login system, which resulted in multiple accounts for a single user, duplicated data, and alternate hashing mechanisms—when even present—for passwords. To address this, scripts were generated for importing of the data into a common account, checking for duplicate information from the various sub-applications and making revisions as needed, while tagging accounts as to their original source. Authentication plugins were then added to the CMS that would allow a one-time login

with the previous hashing mechanism, identified by the aforementioned account tagging, and update the user's information in conformance to the new processes. This would allow for a seamless transition when a user logged into the new system.

The third application type, interactive single-page apps, could largely be ported as-is due to being composed of JavaScript libraries and API data sources. Where appropriate, multiple pages were combined into a single page with extra filters and options. During the porting process, developers noted that much of the images and data being used could, in fact, be generated on demand or retrieved from other, existing sources. Doing so reduced time in processing and removed the need for numerous scripts and file storage.

D. Documentation & Code Management

The originating authors and thought processes for much of the old system and scripts of the MRCC gateway were lost over time to employee-turnover. As such, much of the functionality required reverse-engineering, code tracing, and inspection of logs to determine not only how best to refactor the code but to ensure that refactoring was a success. Consequently, documenting the technologies used, decisions made, setups and purposes of scripts involved was a strong underlying current of the entire process.

All code was committed to GIT repositories with relevant in-code comments, README files detailing purposes and interactions, and external documentation instructing on the setup and use of the various frameworks and platforms involved. While writing such documentation is often considered unpleasant or left to a more convenient time, it was deemed crucial to the success of the project, both current and future.

In association with the documentation and code versioning, one-on-one tutorials and consultation were employed to ensure knowledge transfer to the MRCC team.

IV. ON-GOING WORK

The technologies in the re-architecture of the gateway were chosen in order to benefit the present and future members of the MRCC. Although portions make use of some Purdue-specific services, such as the Geddes composable platform, the underlying tools and documentation allow for potential re-implementation on alternate providers such as Amazon Web Services.

While significant strides have been made thus far, there remains much work to be done, particularly in workflow management for processing and storage of the data underlying many of the gateway applications. Reorganization of how the data is stored could significantly reduce resources and duplication of files. As discovered in the refactoring of one such application, some current processing may simply not be needed or the output of the processing may change. The prior system generated numerous raster maps that resulted in significant file space usage. Ideas being discussed include altering output files to just the data representation and generating the map on demand with JavaScript + HTML canvas, rotating files to varying levels of storage on a hot/warm/cold status by usage.

Future work, both on the MRCC and other potential gateways, will be informed by the lessons that came out of the work to date:

1) *Plan on expansion*: While it can be difficult to predict the success or direction a gateway may take, organize data and code around the assumption of growth and the addition of features/functionality.

2) *Document as much as possible*: This ranges from comments in code to README files to wikis. Even if it's believed only one person will ever work on the code, it's likely that past decisions or reasoning can be forgotten and can benefit enormously from something to reference.

3) *Keep it consistent*: When possible, follow existing code styles, formatting, and architecture. If these can't be followed, document why not.

4) *Avoid personalized settings and locations*: Projects change hands and expect that those working on the gateway now may not be there tomorrow. This includes not running scripts from a home directory, using a personalized account for 3rd-party services (e.g., Google Analytics), hard-coding email addresses, etc.

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